

An Analysis of Youth Character Building Applied by Learner Centered Method: A Case Study of Workshop 21st century Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values) in Medan, Indonesia

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Abstract — The rationale of this research is a lot of efforts already undertaken by the government in building youth character but not yet showing expected results. The situation happens because Indonesia still using traditional learning methods which focus almost exclusively on cognitive domains and pay less attention to the physical and social-emotional domain. Researcher observed that learner centered method is an effective method to build youth character, motivation and creativity that intertwined cooperation and efforts to support each other. The purpose of this qualitative and survey case study research is to gain an understanding of learner centered method's implementation in building character. Samples of the research were ten participants and one trainer from purposive sample, and primary data collection tools are semi-structured interviews. Individual interviews conducted to obtain the appropriate depth interview participants' perception from different backgrounds and life experiences. Data analysis is conducted through three processes: description, reduction and interpretation by using content analysis method and a case-oriented replication strategy to analyze the results of case study data. The findings in this study were (1) the method used to facilitate the active involvement of participants are explanations, discoveries, open-ended questions, demonstrations, discussions, brainstorming, role plays, participation, games and debates which applied by using learner centered method. (2) The acquisition skills of the participants in the training are self-esteem, self-awareness, assertiveness, friendship, empathy, negotiation, communication, creative thinking, critical thinking and problem-solving.

Keywords — *Lifelong Guidelines; Lifeskills (universal values); Training; Learner Centered Method; Character Building and Youth.*

I. INTRODUCTION

This research is about the analysis of youth character building training by applying learning methods in the Workshop 21st Century Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values). This study discusses the development of youth capabilities that have been practiced during the training as well as the assessment of youth character building training that applied learner centered methods. Researchers see the importance of learner centered methods in character building training as an effective method in order to prepare youth for the challenges of the future and to find the meaning and purpose of life.

The paradigm of learner centered method shifts the traditional learning into more focus on the participants and more on learning than on teaching. Thus, the class will become more egalitarian; more emphasis on critical thinking, active learning, and based on the real world.

The constructivism as observed by Marincovich as in [1] is believed to be the beginning of learner centered method. In addition to Taber as in [2] who has a constructivist understanding, [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9] presents different things but the same in principle about constructivist learning, such as:

a. Trainers create a learning environment that allows participants the flexibility and freedom to interact, there is a

great opportunity for them to participate effectively in building knowledge;

b. Trainers use the topic of learning as a catalyst to develop the creativity and critical thinking of the participants and relate it to their daily lives so that they can think outside of themselves;

c. A shift from traditional to learner centered method and the trainer-dominated into a more facilitative and participatory class;

d. Learners are responsible for their own learning which facilitated by the trainer so that participants understand the potential of their learning. Trainer also use assessments and strategies to get the active involvement of participants in building their knowledge;

d. Previous learners' knowledge and experience is the basis for active pedagogical trainer reasoning, as well as practice and decision making; the trainer influences the involvement of learners' social interactions in the process of building knowledge;

e. The need for activities in learning centered method on the participants is to develop the active involvement of participants in building knowledge;

f. The learner uses his life-based knowledge and experience to interpret meaningfully about the concepts and principles of the material so that the participant does not acquire passively but the result of the mind's metacognition of the learner; and

g. The acquisition of knowledge is a process related to biology and development as well as sociocultural, and the phenomenon of language-based interaction.

Stallings [10] found a positive effort to improve youth learning achievement through freedom, diligence in duty, cooperation, and the ability to ask questions. Etzioni and Ginsburg, Hanson. [11], [12] suggest that disciplined or more religious youth are able to work harder and achieve higher learning achievement on academic examinations. Wynne [13] argue that good character should be the main focus of higher academic achievement in youth education so as to reduce their alienation from the environment.

McBrien [14] state that the goal of character building is to educate participants to be morally responsible and to be disciplined citizens, problem solvers, decision-makers, and conflict resolutions that are an essential part in developing moral character. By playing roles and discussions, participants can see that their decisions can affect something and others.

Therefore, by teaching character by using learner centered methods in schools, universities, training and modeling in all walks of life, participants can recognize the importance of having good character wherever they are.

Today's youth are future leaders and citizens, if schools and society can educate youth into high-character people then a country will eventually become a nation of high character.

Research Question:

How is the process of character building training applied by learner centered methods in Workshop 21st Century Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values)?

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research is a qualitative case study which means the information for this research is collected through qualitative method with case study as an action.

This study used purposive samples from one trainer and ten participants. The trainer is an experienced, trained, and experienced expert. The trainer has 30 (thirty) years of experience as an administrator, educator and teacher trainer on the island of Galang for refugees from Vietnam, Laos, and Khmer. She also taught in Utica, New York, Andover, New Hampshire, South Kent, Connecticut and Brattleboro, Vermont. She is retired from Jakarta International School. Experience is important in the application of training because in this case the method used to shift the traditional method. Researcher see the trainer has a strategy that fits the social and cultural conditions in Indonesia.

Including here researcher physically present and monitor the phenomenon that occurs during the course of the training so as to enable researchers to respond and report on the emerging aspects of events and behaviors during the course of the training while gathering as much information as needed.

Workshop 21st Century Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values) has characteristics that are considered relevant to overcome the learning phenomenon and generate more information, such as:

- Participants have been trained using learner-centered methods;
- The trainer has intervened on the participants by using learner-centered methods;
- Methods and materials are applied by using learner-centered methods.

TABEL 1. DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUE

Research Question	Method	Data Collection	Data Collection Strategy	Results
How is the process of character building training applied by learner centered methods in Workshop 21 st Century Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values)?	Qualitative	Interviews and instruments of direct observation	1. Interview with the trainer 2. Observation of the skills gained through activities on the course planner	1. The method used in the training 2. Characters that indicate participants who demonstrate ability

III. RESULT

TABELE 2. CATEGORY OF RESPONDENTS

No	Category of respondents	Amount	Code
1	Trainer	1	PL
2	Participants with perception of new methods	3	PSM 001-070
3	Participants with new perception experience	7	PSP 001-137

In Workshop 21stCentury Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values), there are one trainer and ten participants who were successfully interviewed by the researcher. Each trainer and participant is given initials to protect the identity of the respondent.

TABEL 3. COURSE PLANNER OBSERVATION

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Observation	Activity in course planner	Instruction	Tools and materials used	Skills developed
1	Introduction and brain gym	Explanation, participation	None	Mental and physical activity, self-esteem, communication
2	The Human bingo, Ice breaker	Writing, participation, demonstration	None	Cooperation, critical thinking, communication, self-esteem, friendship
3	Workshop overview Assessment Criteria	Open-ended questions, demonstration	None	Critical thinking, problem-solving, decision making
4	The umbrella activity/Perception	Demonstration, participation	None	Critical thinking, problem-solving, decision making
5	The favorite teacher criteria and the Favorite student criteria (round table activity)	Brainstorming, open-ended questions, explanation, discussion	None	Friendship, assertiveness, empathy, communication, critical thinking
6	Lifelong Guidelines and Life Skills Presentation/Round robin activity (presentation)	Explanation, demonstration	Handout	Friendship, assertiveness, self-awareness, empathy, critical thinking, problem-

				solving and decision making
7	Trustworthiness, Truthfulness, Active Listening, No Put Downs and Doing Your Best. Round robin Group Presentation	Demonstration, discussion	Handout	Self-awareness, friendship, assertiveness, empathy
8	a song "My Favorite Things"	Sing, demonstration	Handout	Communication, assertiveness
9	Group making Yel, yel!	Writing	Large Paper	Creativity, friendship, communication, critical thinking, leadership, decision making
10	The Inside-outside circle.	Games	Cue cards	Reinforcement of material, critical thinking, decision making
11	A skit on Life skills	Demonstration, role play	Training Material	Review and reinforce material
12	To write a song about life skills Presentations of the song each group	Writing	Large Paper	Friendship, assertiveness, self-awareness, empathy, critical thinking, problem-solving and decision making
13	In groups discuss Multiple Intelligence followed by group presentation	Explanation, open-ended questions, demonstration	Handout	Empathy, friendship, decision making, , communication, assertiveness, self-awareness
14	Metacognitive Journal	Writing	Journal Form	Critical thinking, creativity
15	Exit card	Writing	Cards	Critical thinking

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Observation	Activity in course planner	Instruction	Tools and materials used	Skills developed
16	Brain Gym	Demonstration	None	Mental and physical activity, friendship
17	Review	Open-ended questions	None	Critical thinking, problem-solving, decision making, reinforcement and review of material, communication
18	Work in groups to discuss Multiple Intelligence/ presentation	Discussion, open-ended questions	None	Empathy, friendship, decision making, communication, assertiveness, self-awareness
19	Filling out instrument	Writing	None	Critical thinking, self-esteem, assertiveness, self-awareness
20	Reading from Dr. Howard Garner	open-ended questions, demonstration, explanation	None	Critical thinking, communication, empathy
21	Sing a M.I song	Demonstration, participation	None	Empathy, communication, assertiveness

22	Read and discuss Habits of Mind in groups	Open-ended questions, demonstration, explanation	Ppt, guidebooks	Empathy, friendship, decision making, material reading
23	In groups create a three dimension object using all the materials available.	Discussion, participation, demonstration	Training Material	Communication, creativity, critical thinking, negotiation, decision making
24	Reflective Journal	Writing	Homeworks	Critical thinking, self-esteem, assertiveness, communication
25	Feedback/Wrap-Up/exit	Discussion, open-ended questions	None	Communication, assertiveness, critical thinking, self-esteem, self-awareness, assertiveness

TABLE 4. OBSERVATION OF MATERIALS AND ACTIVITIES

Training Material	Learning	Skills	Category	Character indicator
Lifelong Guidelines	Emotional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trustworthiness - Truthfulness - Active listening - No put downs - Doing my personal best 	self-esteem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express likes and dislikes - Self-esteem - Talk about himself/herself
				self-awareness
			assertiveness	
Lifeskills	Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Friendship - Problem-solving - Curiosity - Effort - Organization 		friendship formation

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation - Caring - Courage - Patience - Common sense - Pride - Flexibility - Integrity - Responsibility - Resourceful - Initiative - Perseverance - Sense of humor 	<hr/> <p>empathy</p> <hr/> <p>negotiation</p> <hr/> <p>communication</p> <hr/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supporting other participants - Care for other participants - Using the polite language - Listen to others - Fun - Guiding other participants <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using persuasive language - Using proper body language - Controlling temperament - Respond appropriately - Apologize - Make a request - Appreciation <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fluency - Listening skills - Meaningfulness - Confidence - Articulation - Precision - Logical flow of ideas - Language - Gesture <hr/>
Habits of Mind	Cognitive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Persisting - Managing impulsivity - Listening to others with understanding - Thinking about our thinking (<i>metacognition</i>) - Striving for accuracy - Questioning and Posing Problems - Applying past knowledge to new situation - Thinking and communicationg with clarity and precision - Gathering all data through all senses - Creating, imagining and innovating - Responding with wonderment and awe - Taking responsible risk - Finding humor 	<hr/> <p>creative thinking</p> <hr/> <p>critical thinking</p> <hr/> <p>problem-solving</p> <hr/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Logical reasoning - Innovative - Find new ways of doing things <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responding to questions correctly - Selecting and evaluating information - Analyze statements - Reasoning for the actions taken - Decision making - Use the information that is owned with the best <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decision making - Evaluate the facts <hr/>

A. *TRAINER'S PERCEPTION OF THE TRAINING IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS*

TABLE 5. THE INITIAL THEME OF THE INTERVIEW WITH THE TRAINER

Research Question	Category	Theme
How is the process of character building training applied by learner centered methods in Workshop 21 st Century Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values)?	Facilitator	Activating learner
		Traditional method
		Cooperative learning
		Training material
		Learning by doing
		Project based learning
		Role play
		Round robin
		Life experiences
		Participant's attitude
		Responsibility on his/her learning

TABLE 6. FINAL THEME OF THE INTERVIEW WITH THE TRAINER

Research Question	Category	Theme
The process of character building training applied by learner centered methods in Workshop 21 st Century Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values)	Facilitator	Independent learner
		Class management
		Instructional strategy

IV. DISCUSSION

A. *OBSERVATION*

The methods, training materials and life skills trained are represented the trainer's strategy plan in training character building during the teaching and learning process.

The relationship between the skills developed and the activities in this training is only found in the learning activities. For example, in observation 6, each character building activity is described as follows:

At the 25 (twenty five) activities in the course planner observed, the participants demonstrated the skills that is trained. In observation 6, the activities in which the participants were given the task of writing a participant's understanding of the skills in the training materials on TABLE 3, the participants behaved that showed how critical

thinking, friendship, assertiveness, self-awareness, empathy and problem solving both before and during the presentation sessions work in group.

B. *INTERVIEW WITH THE TRAINER*

1. Independent learner

An independent learner is trained in his class by cooperative learning method (PL 017) and the activities in the training facilitate the participants to become independent learners (observation 5, 6, 7, 10, 12, 13, 14, 18, 22, 23, 24).

2. Class management

When learner centered class compared with traditional classroom management then we can see that the participant is activated (PL 005) and all activities have been planned (PL 010) and each participant gets the same chance (PL

014). This can be seen throughout the training activities (observation 5, 6, 7, 10, 12, 13, 14, 18, 22, 23, 24).

3. Instructional strategy

In teaching the training material (PL 019), trainer use a variety of instructions (observation 1 to 16 dan observation 18 to 25). But in order to build the character, the most important thing is life experiences (PL 009) and the best method is learning by doing (PL 007). Such as round robin activities (observation 8) which use learner centered method which allowed every participant gets the same opportunity and free to express his/her opinion (PL 011). And in character building, there must be result shown in PBL (project based learning) or can be replaced with role play (PL 008).

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMENDATION

A. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of interviews with trainer and the results of observation done by the researcher on the training of character building in Workshop 21st Century Fluency Skills Education, Lifelong Guidelines and Lifeskills (Universal Values) found that in the training there is a dynamic learning process. The methods used to facilitate the active involvement of the participants are explanations, discoveries, open-ended questions, demonstrations, discussions, brainstorming, role plays, participation, games and debates that are all applied with learner-centered methods.

B. RECOMMENDATION

Character building is basically a skill that helps provide overall wellbeing and youth's ability to face the realities of life. Character-building training can be successful if done with a learner-centered method.

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